

“A Study of Virtual Banking in India”

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Abstract:

The Revolution in transportation technology in transportation technology has revolutionized the world's industrial and agricultural sectors, and in all of this, the rapid revolution in the banking sector has led to virtual banking. Attempts have been made to change the face of the banking sector. The study collected data from primary and secondary sources. Online banking services like ATM, Personal computer Banking. Phone Banking and E-mail Banking will help people to get information and awareness. This paper shows that the introduction of virtual banking in India. The term virtual banking includes e-banking (mobile banking or banking through computers), debit and credit cards, card-swipe or point of sale machines and digital wallet system. It also explains the important theoretical points related to various modes of virtual banking and its trend.

Keywords: Virtual Banking, Electronic channels, Benefits, Trends.

Introduction:

Banking industry in India has also achieved a new height with the changing times. Information technology has given rise to new innovation in the products designing and their delivery in the banking and finance industries. Financial innovation associated with technological change to Tally changed the banking philosophy and that is further tuned by the competition in the banking industry. Virtual Banking also known as internet banking, E-Banking or virtual banking, in an electronic payment system that enables customers of a bank or other financial transaction through the financial institution's website. Internet banking services introduced so for include the ability to monitor account balances, transfer funds between accounts, pay bills, and apply for loans. Only few banks will allow customers to make electronic trades through brokerage accounts. A Virtual bank is a bank that offers banking services through electronic channels. All services of virtual banks can be performed online and there are no bricks-and-mortar branches. Clients can open an account, make deposits, taking out loans and performs other banking transactions via a mobile app or through the website of the virtual bank. Within the near future many banks will offer home banking via an interactive website.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To understand the concept of virtual banking.
2. To study the modes of transactions in virtual banking and its trend in India.

Research Methodology of the Research Paper:

The present study is based on secondary data. This data has used for getting a real result from research paper. Secondary data has been collected from the various RBI Annual Report, Books, Journals and Government Web-Portal.

Modes of transaction in Virtual Banking:

The cashless Economy in India has been amplified with the Indian Government's initiative of Digital India. This is a flagship programme with a vision to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. When the transactions in an economy are not heavily based on the money notes, coins or any other physical form of money but are aided by the use of credit cards, debit cards and prepaid payment instruments, such an economy is called cashless economy. The modes of transactions in virtual banking are as follows.

ATM – Automatic teller Machine:

Automatic Teller machine began to be introduced in the period 1969 -1984 all over the world ATM literally means electronic cash Dispensing, which is open round the clock and 365 day a year. The banks give an ATM cards to the user and allot a separate and identification number

Privet sector banks are going ahead aggressive ATM Plans Particularly off-site for wider reach with lower cost. They are also targeting ATM development in the top corporate offices or staff colonies – not only for the salary accounts but also for a piece of the corporate pie and also to get the find following benefits-

- Reduction in transaction cost
- Reduction in paperwork involved in transfer of securities
- Right location of the ATMs
- Optimum population of ATMs at each Center

Table No.1, Branches and ATMs of Scheduled Commercial Banks (At end-March 2021)

Sr. No.	Name of the Banks	Branches					ATMs		
		Rural	Semi urban	Urban	Metropolitan	Total	On-Site	Off-Site	Total
	Public Sector Banks	28,828	24,028	16,654	16,801	86,311	78,007	59,106	1,37,113
1	Bank of Baroda	2,851	2,087	1,482	1,794	8,214	8,663	2,970	11,633
2	Bank of India	1,835	1,455	803	932	5,025	2,388	3,163	5,551
3	Bank of Maharashtra	611	461	372	471	1,915	1,505	445	1,950
4	Canara Bank	3,072	3,141	2,103	2,130	10,446	9,128	4,324	13,452
5	Central Bank of India	1,603	1,333	810	862	4,608	2,746	898	3,644
6	Indian Bank	1,940	1,589	1,259	1,214	6,002	4,239	686	4,925
7	Indian Overseas Bank	902	961	651	687	3,201	2,720	425	3,145
8	Punjab And Sind Bank	570	279	356	326	1,531	1,067	30	1,097
9	Punjab National Bank	3,900	2,680	2,257	1,931	10,768	8,610	5,171	13,781
10	State Bank of India	7,914	6,496	3,981	3,830	22,221	25,706	36,911	62,617
11	Uco Bank	1,074	818	609	555	3,056	2,146	215	2,361
12	Union Bank of India	2,556	2,728	1,971	2,069	9,324	9,089	3,868	12,957
	Total								

Source- RBI Bulletin

The table shows that, How many ATMs in public sector banks used in march 2021. In Rural branches, Semi urban branches, urban and Metropolitan Branches total use of ATMs On-side and Off- side are 1,37,113.

Credit Card:

In the process of evolution of money after paper currency, several forms of bank money of credit money came in to existence. The quality of these forms of money is the Convince in carrying and effecting the transaction. In this process of evolution, which incidentally, is a continuous process one latest from to enter in to the Indian financial system is credit card.

Benefits of credit cards –

1. To the Banker :

For the issuing banker credit card means an opportunity of making good Profit between the date of payment to business establishment and date of realization of the amount from the card holder period of 30 to 45 days is required.

2. To the member Establishment :

- i) Their sales increase and so do their profits.
- ii) They can sell goods on credit but not at their own risk.
- iii) Their payment is guaranteed by the issuing banker.

3. To the card – holder :

- i) Many banks allow withdrawals of cash against credit cards at any of their beaches.
- ii) In case of loss, the holder's liability is limited.

Debit Card:

Debit cards combine the function of ATM cards and Check. Debit cards are issued by banks but are used at stores, not at the banks themselves. When you pay with a debit cards, the money is

automatically deducted from your account. Debit cards, as we all know are very much in use in resent time. They have eliminated the need for carrying physical cash all around. Not only do they make transaction and paying easy in a matter of seconds ,but also, they are widely accepted.

Benefits of Debit Cards-

- Debit cards are extremely simple to use. Since the payment is deducted directly from your bank account a place where the money already exists, it can be done instantly.
- You pay your bill immediately, unlike when you use a credit card and get bill later.

Internet Banking: In Indian slowly but steadily, the Indian customer is moving to words internet banking a number of banks have either adopted internet banking on the threshold of adopting it. The banks started Internet banking initially with simple function such as getting information about interest rates, checking account balance and computing loan eligibility.

It was ICICI bank which initiated the electronic banking revolution in India when they introduced internet banking as early as 1997 under the HDFC in sept.1999. Global trust bank etc. as estimated 4.6 million Indian Internet users are banking through internet. This figure is expected to reach around 16 million by 2007-08.

SWIFT (society for worldwide interbank financial telecommunication :

SWIFT is the global financial community's foremost messaging infrastructure that is lowest risk and highest flexibility. SWIFT'S mission is to become a worldwide community of financial institution whose purpose is to be the leader in communication solution enabling inter-

operability between its members, their market infrastructure and their end-user community. In 2003 SWIFT had revenue of EUR 57 million and had assets worth EUR 413 million and had 1708 employees. It has reached 2 billion message marks. The growth rate in message traffic is 16.69%. It covers over 200 countries and the live users are over 7500.

RTGS – Real time gross settlement:

RTGS system was introduced in India on 26th march, 2004. RTGS system is a comprehensive and secured online payment mechanism.

Under RTGS system is interbank payment instruction are processed throughout the day, on transaction- by transaction basis. RTGS system was set up, operated and managed by Reserve Bank of India (RBI).

Benefits-

- a) For minimizing the cost of transfer of funds
- b) For reducing the risk of transfer of funds
- c) For providing liquidity to the beneficiary.

Digital Payments:

Large value credit transfers through RTGS dominated the overall payments landscape in the year 2019-20, according for 80.8% of the total value of digital transaction. In terms of volume however, credit transfer via multiple channels such as a unified Payments Interface (UPI), National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT) and Immediate Payment Service (IMPS) were the leaders. In case of card payments, the value of card transaction registered a growth of 35.6 % against 21.1% for credit cards.

Table No-2, Digital Payments

	Volume(Lakh)			Value(crore)		
	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
1. Large Value Credit Transfers – RTGS	1244	1,366	1,507	11,67,12,478	13,56,88,187	13,11,56,475
2. Credit Transfers	58,793	1,18,750	2,06,661	1,88,14,287	2,60,97,655	2,85,72,100
2.1 AePS	6	11	10	300	501	469
2.2 APBS	12,980	15,032	16,805	55,949	86,734	99,448
2.3 ECS Cr	61	54	18	11,864	13,235	5,145
2.4 IMPS	10,098	17,529	25,792	8,92,498	15,90,257	23,37,541
2.5 NACH Cr	7,031	9,021	11,406	5,20,992	7,36,349	10,52,187
2.6 NEFT	19,464	23,189	27,445	1,72,22,852	2,27,93,608	2,29,45,580
2.7 UPI	9,152	53,915	1,25,186	1,09,832	8,76,971	21,31,730
3. Debit Transfers and Direct Debits	3,788	6,382	8,957	3,99,300	6,56,232	8,26,036
3.1 BHIM Aadhaar Pay	20	68	91	78	815	1303
3.2 ECS Dr	15	9	1	972	1260	39
3.3 NACH Dr	3,738	6,299	8,768	3,98,211	6,54,138	8,24,491
3.4 NETC	15	6	97	39	20	203
4. Card Payments	47,486	61,769	73,012	9,19,035	11,96,888	15,35,765
4.1 Credit Cards	14,052	17,626	21,773	4,58,965	6,03,413	7,30,895
4.2 Debit Cards	33,434	44,143	51,239	4,60,070	5,93,475	8,04,870
5. Prepaid Payments Instruments	34,591	46072	53,318	1,41,634	2,13,323	2,15,558
Total Digital Payments(1+2+3+4+5)	1,45902	2,34,339	3,43,456	13,69,86,734	16,38,52,286	16,23,05,934

Source- RBI Bulletin

The table clear that, India is in progressive step in terms of using Digital Payments . RTGS has made digital payments of Rs. 11,67,12,478 crore in 2017-18, while it has increased to Rs. 13,11,56,475 crore in 2019-20. In the last three years the valume of Total Digital Payments of RTGS , Credit Transfers ,Debit Transfer and Direct Debits, Cards Payments, Prepaid Payments Instruments in 2017-18 it was 1,45902 , in 2018-19 it was 2,34,339 and 2019-20 it was 3,43,456 lakhs . Similarly in last three years the volume of Digital Payments is 2017-18 it was

13,69,86,734 , 2018-19 it was 16,38,52,286 and 2019-20 it was 16,23,05,934 crore respectively.

Conclusion:

The banking industry is now a very mature one and banks being forced to change rapidly as a result of open market forces such as threat of competition, customer demand, and technological innovation such as growth of internet banking. If banks have to retain their competitiveness, they must focus on customer retention and relationship management upgrade and offer integration and value added services.

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